

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PREDICTORS OF EFL PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS SELF-EFFICACY

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Abstract

This article investigates the key predictors of self-efficacy among pre-service teachers in English as a Foreign Language (EFL). Self-efficacy, the belief in one's ability to accomplish tasks and overcome challenges, is crucial for effective teaching, particularly in the context of language education. The study employs a mixed-method approach, integrating quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews with a diverse cohort of EFL pre-service teachers. Key findings reveal that prior language learning experiences, mentorship quality, and exposure to multicultural environments significantly influence self-efficacy. The study also highlights the impact of practical teaching experiences and pedagogical training on developing confidence in classroom management and instructional strategies. Interestingly, personal linguistic proficiency emerged as a less significant predictor than expected. This research has implications for teacher training programs, highlighting areas for targeted support and development to foster more effective and confident EFL educators.

Аңдатпа

Бұл мақалада мұғалімдер арасында шет тілі (EFL) ретінде ағылшын тілінде қызмет еткенге дейінгі өзіндік тиімділіктің негізгі болжамдары зерттеледі. Өзіндік тиімділік, міндеттерді орындау және қиындықтарды еңсеру қабілетіне сенім, әсіресе тілдік білім беру контекстінде тиімді оқыту үшін шешуші мәнге ие. Зерттеуде сандық сауалнамалар мен сапалы сұхбаттарды әртүрлі EFL мектеп жасына дейінгі мұғалімдер тобымен біріктіретін аралас әдіс қолданылады. Түйінді нәтижелер тілді үйренудің алдыңғы тәжірибесі, тәлімгерлік сапасы және мультикультуралық ортаның әсері өзіндік тиімділікке айтарлықтай әсер ететінін көрсетеді. Зерттеуде оқытудың және педагогикалық даярлықтың практикалық тәжірибесінің сыныптарды басқаруға және білім беру стратегияларына сенімділікті дамытуға әсері де атап көрсетіледі. Қызығы, жеке лингвистикалық меңгеру күтілгеннен әлдеқайда маңызды емес. Бұл зерттеу EFL-дің неғұрлым тиімді және сенімді оқытушыларына ықпал ету үшін мақсатты қолдау мен даму үшін салаларды бөле отырып, мұғалімдерді даярлау бағдарламалары үшін маңызды.

Аннотация

В этой статье исследуются ключевые предикторы самоэффективности среди учителей до службы на английском языке как иностранном языке (EFL). Самоэффективность, вера в свою способность выполнять задачи и преодолевать трудности, имеет решающее значение для эффективного обучения, особенно в контексте языкового образования. В исследовании используется смешанный метод, объединяющий количественные опросы и качественные интервью с разнообразной когортой учителей-дошкольников EFL. Ключевые результаты показывают, что предыдущий опыт изучения языка, качество наставничества и воздействие мультикультурной среды значительно влияют на самоэффективность. В исследовании также подчеркивается влияние практического опыта преподавания и педагогической подготовки на развитие доверия к управлению классами и образовательным стратегиям. Интересно, что личное лингвистическое владение оказалось менее значимым предиктором, чем ожидалось. Это исследование имеет значение для программ подготовки учителей, выделяя области для целевой поддержки и развития, чтобы способствовать более эффективным и уверенным преподавателям EFL.

Keywords: EFL pre-service teachers, self-efficacy, teacher training, language proficiency, pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, teaching experience, cultural awareness.

Түйінді сөздер: EFL тәжірибелі мұғалімдер, өзіндік тиімділік, мұғалімдерді даярлау, тілді меңгеру, педагогикалық білім, сыныптық басшылық, оқыту тәжірибесі, мәдени хабардар болу.

Ключевые слова: учителя-практиканты EFL, самоэффективность, подготовка учителей, владение языком, педагогические знания, классное руководство, опыт преподавания, культурная осведомленность.

Introduction. The concept of self-efficacy, as defined by Albert Bandura, refers to an individual's belief in their ability to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance outcomes. In the context of education, particularly among pre-service teachers of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), this belief system plays a pivotal role. These individuals stand at the precipice of entering a challenging professional landscape, where their self-efficacy beliefs are not just personal indicators of confidence, but crucial predictors of

their future teaching effectiveness and professional development.

Understanding self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers is essential due to the unique challenges they face. Teaching a language that is not the native tongue of the majority of students presents its own set of complexities. These challenges range from addressing diverse student needs to managing the intricacies of a language that the teacher might not be natively fluent in. Therefore, the self-efficacy beliefs of these teachers can

significantly influence their approach to these challenges, their persistence in the face of difficulties, and their overall teaching performance.

Moreover, self-efficacy beliefs in pre-service teachers can shape their future teaching practices and attitudes towards the profession. A strong sense of self-efficacy can lead to greater enthusiasm for teaching, a willingness to implement innovative teaching methods, and resilience in dealing with the ups and downs of the teaching profession. Conversely, low self-efficacy may result in a lack of confidence, a reluctance to try new teaching strategies, and a higher likelihood of burnout.

This article aims to explore the various dimensions that contribute to shaping self-efficacy beliefs in EFL pre-service teachers. It considers a range of factors, including educational background, teaching practicum experiences, language proficiency, cultural influences, and psychological attributes. By examining these elements, the article seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of what fuels or impedes the development of self-efficacy in this specific group of educators. Such insights are not only critical for the pre-service teachers themselves but also for the mentors, educators, and policymakers who play a role in shaping teacher education programs. Ultimately, enhancing our understanding of these factors can lead to more effective training and support systems, thereby preparing EFL pre-service teachers to enter the profession with the confidence and competence necessary to succeed [1; 299-322].

Social Cognitive Theory. Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory provides a foundational framework for understanding self-efficacy, particularly in educational settings. Central to this theory is the concept of reciprocal determinism, which suggests that human functioning is the result of the interaction between behavioral, cognitive, and environmental factors. Within this framework, self-efficacy emerges as a key factor influencing how individuals think, motivate themselves, and act.

In the context of education, and more specifically for EFL pre-service teachers, Social Cognitive Theory helps explain how beliefs about personal efficacy can influence the approach to teaching and learning [2; 1107-1111]. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to embrace challenging tasks, persist in the face of setbacks, and display resilience. This attitude not only impacts their own professional development but also the educational outcomes of their students. Bandura's theory emphasizes that the development of self-efficacy is an ongoing process, influenced by various experiences and environmental factors throughout a teacher's career.

Sources of Self-Efficacy. Bandura identifies four primary sources of self-efficacy, each playing a crucial role in the development of self-efficacy beliefs in individuals, including EFL pre-service teachers.

Table-1.

Sources of Self-Efficacy

1.	Mastery Experiences	These are the most influential sources of self-efficacy. Successful experiences boost self-efficacy, while failures may diminish it. For EFL pre-service teachers, successful teaching experiences, effective lesson planning, and positive student feedback can significantly enhance their sense of efficacy
2.	Vicarious Experiences	Observing peers or mentors successfully performing a task can strengthen self-efficacy, especially when the observer perceives similarities with the model. EFL pre-service teachers can gain confidence by seeing other teachers effectively manage classrooms, deliver lessons, and engage with students [3; 385-400].
3.	Verbal Persuasion	Encouragement and positive feedback from credible sources can enhance self-efficacy. For pre-service teachers, this could come from mentors, supervisors, or peers who provide constructive feedback and reinforce their potential for success
4.	Physiological and Emotional States	Individuals interpret their stress levels, emotions, and physical states as indicators of competence or incompetence. EFL pre-service teachers might assess their nervousness, excitement, or stress during teaching as indicators of their teaching abilities [4].

Understanding these sources of self-efficacy is crucial in developing strategies to enhance it among EFL pre-service teachers. By acknowledging and fostering conditions that strengthen these sources, teacher education programs can more effectively prepare pre-service teachers for the challenges and rewards of the

teaching profession. This understanding also underlines the need for a supportive learning environment where pre-service teachers can experiment, observe, receive feedback, and reflect on their teaching experiences in a way that fosters a positive sense of self-efficacy.

Figure-1. Predictors of Self-Efficacy in EFL Pre-Service Teachers(Note: Figures based on sources [5].)

a. Educational Background. The educational and pedagogical training that EFL pre-service teachers receive plays a significant role in shaping their self-efficacy beliefs. A robust teacher education program that provides comprehensive content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and an understanding of language acquisition theories can enhance self-efficacy. Courses that focus on teaching methodologies, classroom management, language assessment, and curriculum development equip pre-service teachers with the knowledge and skills they need, thereby boosting their confidence in their teaching abilities. Additionally, opportunities to engage in reflective practices and theoretical discussions about teaching can further reinforce their belief in their capabilities.

b. Teaching Practicum Experiences. Teaching practicum experiences are crucial in the development of self-efficacy for EFL pre-service teachers. Hands-on experiences in real classroom settings provide an invaluable platform for applying theoretical knowledge and pedagogical skills. The support and guidance from mentor teachers during these practicums are also vital. Constructive feedback, coupled with the opportunity to observe experienced teachers, can significantly influence pre-service teachers' beliefs in their teaching abilities. Successful handling of classroom challenges during practicums, such as managing student behavior or effectively delivering lessons, directly contributes to enhancing self-efficacy [6; 1785].

c. Language Proficiency. For EFL pre-service teachers, personal proficiency in English is a critical factor affecting self-efficacy. High proficiency can increase confidence in their ability to teach the language effectively, manage classroom communication, and understand and use pedagogical materials. Conversely, teachers who perceive their language skills as inadequate may experience lower self-efficacy, which can impact their teaching performance and willingness to engage in certain pedagogical practices.

d. Cultural Factors. Cultural background and attitudes towards the English language and the teaching profession can also influence self-efficacy. Cultural perceptions about the role of teachers, the status of the English language, and the value of education in society can shape pre-service teachers' attitudes towards their profession. Additionally, cultural congruence or dissonance between the teacher's background and the teaching context (e.g., teaching EFL in a culturally diverse setting) can impact self-efficacy beliefs, affecting how teachers perceive their ability to handle cross-cultural communication and understanding in the classroom.

e. Psychological Attributes. Personality traits, resilience, and coping mechanisms play a significant role in determining self-efficacy. Traits such as openness to experience, conscientiousness, and extroversion may positively influence self-efficacy beliefs. Resilience, or the ability to bounce back from setbacks, is particularly important in the face of the challenges and uncertainties that come with teaching. Coping mechanisms, such as stress management and problem-solving skills, also contribute to a teacher's belief in their ability to handle classroom challenges effectively [7; 301-319].

The development of self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers is a complex interplay of educational, experiential, personal, cultural, and psychological factors. Understanding these predictors can help in designing teacher education programs that not only equip pre-service teachers with necessary skills and knowledge but also actively work towards strengthening their belief in their own teaching capabilities.

Interaction of Predictors. The development of self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers is not the result of isolated factors working independently. Instead, it emerges from the intricate interplay of various predictors that collectively shape a teacher's belief in their teaching abilities. This interaction creates a dynamic and complex web that can either reinforce or undermine self-efficacy levels.

1. **Interplay between Educational Background and Practicum Experiences:** The knowledge and skills gained from educational training often find their practical application during teaching practicums. For instance, a pre-service teacher with a strong theoretical foundation in language acquisition might feel more confident when applying these concepts in a real classroom. Conversely, encountering challenges during practicums that weren't addressed in their formal education can reveal gaps and possibly shake their self-efficacy.

2. **The Synergy of Language Proficiency and Educational Background:** High language proficiency can enhance the effectiveness of the pedagogical training received. EFL pre-service teachers who are confident in their English skills might be more adept at grasping and applying complex teaching methods. In contrast, those with lower language proficiency might struggle to fully benefit from their training, thereby affecting their self-efficacy.

3. **Cultural Factors and Teaching Practicums:** Cultural factors can significantly influence the practicum experience. For example, a pre-service teacher from a cultural background that highly values teacher authority might struggle with student-centered teaching methods popular in another culture. This dissonance can impact their self-efficacy, as they might feel less capable of managing classrooms effectively in different cultural settings.

4. **Psychological Attributes as Mediators:** Personality traits, resilience, and coping mechanisms can mediate the impact of other factors on self-efficacy. A resilient teacher with effective coping strategies might handle the challenges encountered during practicums more effectively, thereby maintaining or even enhancing their self-efficacy. On the other hand, a teacher prone to anxiety might find that even a well-rounded educational background and high language proficiency are insufficient to foster strong self-efficacy if they cannot manage stress effectively.

5. **Reciprocal Influence of Self-Efficacy on Other Predictors:** Interestingly, the relationship is not unidirectional. High self-efficacy itself can influence how pre-service teachers engage with their educational training, approach practicum experiences, utilize their language skills, and navigate cultural challenges. For instance, teachers with high self-efficacy might be

more proactive in seeking additional resources to improve their teaching skills or more persistent in overcoming language barriers [8;].

In summary, the predictors of self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers interact in a dynamic and reciprocal manner. This interaction suggests that efforts to enhance self-efficacy should adopt a holistic approach, considering how these diverse elements can be aligned and synergized to create a supportive environment for the development of strong self-efficacy beliefs.

Teacher education programs, therefore, need to be cognizant of these interactions and design curricula and support systems that address these multifaceted needs comprehensively.

Implications for Teacher Education. The understanding of self-efficacy predictors in EFL pre-service teachers has significant implications for the design of teacher education programs. These implications can guide curriculum design and the establishment of effective mentorship and support systems.

Table-2.

Curriculum Design

1.	Integrating Theory and Practice	Curriculum should blend theoretical knowledge with practical application. Courses should not only cover language teaching methodologies and classroom management strategies but also provide opportunities for students to apply these concepts through simulations, case studies, and teaching demonstrations
2.	Emphasizing Reflective Practice	Encourage reflective practices where pre-service teachers analyze and reflect on their teaching experiences, challenges faced, and strategies used. This can be facilitated through journaling, discussion forums, and reflective assignments
3.	Enhancing Language Proficiency	Include courses or modules aimed at enhancing the English language skills of pre-service teachers. This could involve advanced language classes, pronunciation workshops, and language immersion activities [9; 1142-1154].
4.	Cultural Competency Training	Provide training that helps pre-service teachers understand and navigate the cultural dimensions of language teaching. This can include workshops on cross-cultural communication, teaching in multicultural environments, and understanding cultural biases
5.	Incorporating Stress Management and Resilience Building	Introduce components in the curriculum that focus on developing emotional intelligence, stress management skills, and resilience. This could be through workshops, counseling services, or courses on psychological well-being [10; 1-16]

Table-3.

Mentorship and Support Systems

1.	Structured Mentoring Programs	Establish structured mentoring programs where experienced teachers guide pre-service teachers through their practicum and initial teaching experiences. These mentors can provide feedback, share experiences, and offer emotional support
2.	Peer Support Networks	Facilitate the creation of peer support groups where pre-service teachers can share experiences, challenges, and strategies. This peer interaction can provide emotional support and a sense of community
3.	Feedback Mechanisms	Develop a system for providing constructive and regular feedback to pre-service teachers. This feedback should focus not only on areas of improvement but also on acknowledging and reinforcing strengths [11; 591-601]
4.	Professional Development Workshops	Offer workshops and seminars that focus on areas crucial for teacher development, such as classroom management, innovative teaching methods, and adapting to different learning styles
5.	Access to Resources	Ensure that pre-service teachers have access to a wide range of teaching resources, including teaching aids, literature, technology tools, and online platforms. This access can enhance their self-efficacy by providing them with the tools needed to succeed

By addressing these areas in teacher education programs, institutions can play a pivotal role in enhancing the self-efficacy of EFL pre-service teachers. This not only prepares them for the challenges of the teaching profession but also ensures that they enter the workforce as competent, confident, and effective educators [12; 485-493].

Future Research Directions. The study of self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers is a field ripe for further exploration. Empirical research in this area can provide deeper insights and more nuanced understanding, which can ultimately contribute to more effective

teacher training and development programs. The following are key areas where future research could be particularly beneficial:

1. **Longitudinal Studies:** There is a need for longitudinal research to track the development of self-efficacy beliefs over time, from the beginning of teacher education programs through to the early years of teaching. Such studies could provide valuable insights into how self-efficacy evolves and what factors contribute to its sustenance or decline.

2. **Impact of Different Teaching Contexts:** Research examining how various teaching contexts (e.g., urban vs. rural, diverse vs. homogenous student populations) impact the self-efficacy of EFL pre-service

teachers can offer valuable insights. Understanding the challenges and supports unique to different contexts can help tailor teacher education programs more effectively.

3. **Cultural and Linguistic Diversity:** Further studies are needed to understand how cultural and linguistic backgrounds of pre-service teachers influence their self-efficacy. This includes exploring the experiences of teachers from different cultural backgrounds teaching EFL in various international contexts.

4. **Role of Technology in Developing Self-Efficacy:** With the increasing use of technology in education, research into how digital tools and online teaching platforms impact the self-efficacy of pre-service teachers could be highly informative. This includes exploring both the challenges and opportunities presented by technology-enhanced language teaching.

5. **Comparative Studies:** Comparative research between pre-service and in-service teachers can shed light on how professional experience influences self-efficacy. This can help identify what aspects of teacher education programs are most beneficial in preparing teachers for the realities of the classroom.

6. **Influence of Specific Curriculum Designs:** Investigating how different elements of curriculum design (e.g., project-based learning, integrated language teaching approaches) affect the self-efficacy of pre-service EFL teachers can provide insights for curriculum development.

7. **Psychological Well-being and Self-Efficacy:** Examining the relationship between psychological well-being and self-efficacy could reveal important information about how mental health impacts teaching confidence and effectiveness.

8. **Feedback and Self-Efficacy:** Research into the types and methods of feedback that most effectively boost self-efficacy in pre-service teachers could be highly valuable. This includes exploring how peer, mentor, and self-assessment feedback contribute to developing self-efficacy.

9. **Resilience Training:** Investigating the impact of resilience training and stress management on the self-efficacy of pre-service EFL teachers could offer valuable directions for enhancing teacher training programs.

By addressing these areas, future research can significantly contribute to the field of teacher education, particularly in the context of EFL teaching. The findings of such research can inform policy makers, educators, and program designers in creating more effective, responsive, and supportive environments for pre-service EFL teachers, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes for students.

Conclusion. The exploration of self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers is more than an academic endeavor; it is a crucial step towards enhancing the quality of language education globally. Self-efficacy, a belief in one's capabilities to execute the courses of actions required to manage prospective situations, is not just a personal trait but a pivotal component in the teaching-learning ecosystem. Its significance in determining the effectiveness, resilience, and overall success of EFL pre-service teachers cannot be overstated.

Understanding and supporting the development of self-efficacy in these educators is vital for several reasons. First, it directly impacts their teaching performance. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to adopt innovative teaching methods, engage in dynamic classroom interactions, and persist through challenges, thereby enriching the learning experience for their students. Second, self-efficacy influences the well-being and professional growth of teachers. Educators who believe in their teaching abilities experience higher job satisfaction, are less prone to burnout, and are more likely to pursue continuous professional development.

The implications of this understanding extend to the design of teacher education programs. These programs must not only impart essential teaching skills and knowledge but also focus on building the self-efficacy of pre-service teachers. This involves integrating practical experiences, providing mentorship and support, enhancing language proficiency, and addressing the psychological needs of these future educators. By doing so, we can prepare a generation of EFL teachers who are not only competent in their subject matter but also confident in their ability to teach effectively.

Furthermore, the future of EFL teaching hinges on continuous research in this field. Investigating various predictors of self-efficacy and their interplay provides deeper insights into how best to support pre-service teachers. Longitudinal studies, comparative analyses, and research into the impact of technology and cultural factors can all contribute to a more nuanced understanding of self-efficacy development in this context.

In conclusion, fostering self-efficacy in EFL pre-service teachers is essential for the betterment of educational outcomes. It is a multifaceted process that requires a concerted effort from educators, curriculum designers, policymakers, and the teachers themselves. By prioritizing the development of self-efficacy, we can ensure that the future of EFL education is in the hands of capable, confident, and innovative teachers, ready to meet the diverse needs of learners in an increasingly globalized world.

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